

Gender Discrimination and Its impact on Employee Productivity/Performance (A study on government universities of upper sindh)

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Abstract: *This research paper examines the gender discrimination and its impact on the employees' performance/productivity. Three factors of gender discrimination are included that is discrimination in recruitment and selection, promotion and facilities. Closed ended questionnaire was used. Data was collected from 192 employees of public universities of upper sindh. Quantitative technique regression was used to analysis the data. Results shows that gender discrimination factors are not much contributing towards employee performance, only single variable that is gender discrimination in promotion is positively related with employee performance and level of significance is .001, but the strength of relationship between gender discrimination in promotion and employee performance/productivity is too much weak that is (.240).*

Key Words- Employee Performance/Productivity, Gender Discrimination, facilities, promotion, recruitment and selection
Paper Type -Research Paper

INTRODUCTION:

The word Gender is originally derived from Latin word Genre which means kind, race. Gender is defined as the status of being male, female or neuter also individual's external appearance and behaviors associated to that belief, together with their gender functions and roles (Webster). The word discrimination is also a Latin word and it is defined as unmerited behavior by individual for a human being, ethnic group, class, etc; act based on discrimination. Gender discrimination refers to inequality among individuals because of their gender. It is a situation in which someone is treated less well because of their gender, usually when a woman is treated less well than a man. Because of gender discrimination, girls and women do not have the same opportunities as boys and men for education, meaningful careers, political influence, and economic development. In some societies, this practice is ancient and tolerable to both genders. Certain religious groups hug gender discrimination as part of their belief. On the other hand, in most developed nations, it is either illegal or generally measured wrong (Bukhari & Ramzan, 2013) .

Gender discrimination at the workplace happens when employees are treated in a different way just because of they belong to particular gender and it also affects terms and benefits of employment. For instance change in position, difference in pay, change of title, appointment and termination, promotions etc. Gender discrimination happens from employee but also it can be observed from some colleagues. Marital Status, motherhood, pregnancy or expectation are common causes for Discrimination against female. On the other hand sexual orientation is considered as reason for male discrimination (TAYLOR). Gender discrimination in recruitment, promotion on the basis of gender and gender inequality in allocated facilities have negative relationship with employee performance and will reduce organizational productivity (Abbas, Hameed, & Waheed, October 2011). According to Pakistan's Constitution there is equality among all citizens as per law and It does not allow Inequality because of gender difference and ensures right approach to empower women by their active role in all fields (Kazi, 2011).

The purpose of this study is to measure height of Gender Discrimination and dimensions of Gender Inequality which effects employees' performance in government higher educational institutes of Upper Sindh.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Qaisar, Abdul, & Aamer (2011) described about the gender discrimination and its effect on the employee productivity which directly affected the organization's profitibility by collecting data from two telecom organization one is government(ufone) and other is private multinational organization(telenor) . They found that Gender dicrimination in hiring , promotion and providing facilities to employees have negative relationship with employee performance In order to survive and earn profitibility organization has to avoid gender discrimination in hiring ,promotion and providing facilities to employees .Positive and loyal culture increase the employee productivity and organization profitibility.

Channar, Abbassi, & Ujan (2011) have conducted the research on gender biasesness in workforce and how it impact on employees of Hyderabad and jamshoro districts' private and public health and education departments .they have found that female workers are discriminated more in private sector than public sector. Gender discrimination has positive

relationship with stress and negative with job satisfaction and motivation, commitment and enthusiasm. Gender discrimination decreases the satisfaction, motivation, commitment, enthusiasm and increases the stress of workforce.

Barsha (2007) has conducted research on private organization of pokhara by taken sample of hundred females of different age group .they found that male behavior toward female is positive. Female are self motivates to engaged in organized work and do not perceive sexual harassment, gender discrimination and glass ceiling in organization. Female's attitude is positive and has family support towards career and professional advancement. Mostly females blame socio-culture side for their professional underdevelopment. Female respondents have stronger belief that they have ability to perform challenging task and disagree that males have more abilities to perform office work and their work does not affect their performance at home.

Adhikari (2014) she conducted research on five IT companies of lucknow .She find no significant difference in the performance of different gender employees(male, female) and there is significant level of discrimination at work place female workers are discriminate they are under paid and get less rewards as compare to men which decrease motivation and moral which effect their productivity.

Swimmer (1990) has concluded that female clerical employees are discriminated in getting promotions as compare to male. Results shows that promotion criteria for females clerks is difficult and different as compare to male employees.

Francine & Jed (2007) have found gender difference in promotion rate of getting promotion or higher rank is lower for female employees and also find no gender difference in salary growth attach to promotion.

F., J., & O. (2013) they conducted study on medical doctors of private hospitals in order to analyze the effect of gender bias on productivity. Primary and secondary data are collected and examine through descriptive and inferential statistics results shows that employees who are affect by gender discrimination lose their motivation which directly affect their productivity. Gender discrimination has negative impact on the profitability of private hospital.

Daniel, Adewale, Anthonia, & Olumuyiwa (2014) they concluded that gender discrimination negatively affect employee performance. Female staffs are discriminated by not getting higher level positions or managerial position which affects their performance.

HERSCH & VISCUSI (1996) results indicate that women are getting more promotion than men because women are getting jobs at lower level and this provide more promotion opportunities but promotion is not linked with wage increase for women than men. promotion contribute more wage increase for men.

Margaret & Alison (2009) have found that (white and visible minority) women are less likely to get promotion at lower level of organizational hierarchy and visible minority men are also get less promotion opportunity at lower and higher level of organization hierarchy.

Mustafa & Rabail (2014) they conducted the study at private banking sector in order to examine the gender bias at organization and its affect on female employee and organization productivity performance .they found that gender discrimination has not influence the employee performance and company commitment

Nick (2012) they concluded from the results that female at higher position face fewer barriers to get promotion than female employees at lower or middle position/career level.

JANEEN & WRIGHT(2000) they defined general hypothesis is female employees faced more barrier and difficulties to move up the higher position because of gender discrimination they conducted research to examine this hypothesis. they did not find evidence of glass ceiling effect in usa .

Napari & Antti (2011) they found that females start their career at lower position and earn higher wages as compare to males and men get more promotion opportunity during the first year in labor market which increase gender difference. Male employees get higher benefit from employer change where as female employees benefited from internal promotion..

Deborah (2011) male employees had more likely to receive promotion as compare to female employees, but female employees has higher wage increases linked to promotions

Syed, Shaikh, & Herani (2010) they conduct research on pay discrimination on the basis of gender, decrease the job motivation and satisfaction which causes decrease in employee performance organization performance and causes

problem in employee retention of lower level (blue-collar) workers at manufacturing company. Results conclude that significant relationship between gender bias and Wage dissatisfaction, wages (salaries of female worker is different from male worker) and company's productivity.

Objective of Study: To study gender discrimination in variables recruitment and selection, promotion and facilities and how gender discrimination in these variables impact the employee performance/productivity. This Research will present the relationship between gender bias and employee productivity/performance.

Research model:

HYPOTHESIS AND DIAGNOSTIC TEST:

$$EP = \alpha + GDRS \beta_1 + GDP\beta_2 + GDF\beta_3 + \mu$$

EP= Employee performance/productivity.

α = constant

GDRs =Gender discrimination in recruitment and selection.

GDP= Gender discrimination in promotion.

GDF= Gender discrimination in providing facilities.

μ = standard error.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ =Coefficients.

After reviewing the literature hypothesis is created.

Hypothesis 1:

H1= there is significant relationship between gender discrimination and employee performance/productivity.

Hypothesis 1(a):

Gender discrimination in recruitment and selection is significantly related with employee performance/productivity.

Hypothesis 1(b):

Gender discrimination in promotion is significantly related with employee performance/productivity.

Hypothesis 1(c):

Gender discrimination in facilities is significantly related with employee performance/productivity.

Scope of the Study: This study conducted on public or government universities of upper sindh. This study measured the impact of gender discrimination on employee performance/productivity.

Research Methodology: Data were collected from 192 respondents by the random sample selection. Data were analyzed through spss18 software by using the quantitative technique regression.

Data set:

Primary data: closed ended Questionnaire was designed which consisted of six demographics questions and 24 questions related to variables. Questions were based on five point Likert scale. Starting from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

1 Strongly Disagree 2 Disagree 3 Neutral
 4 Agree 5 Strongly Agree

Secondary data: Different research papers were used for quoting the work related to our data.

Results and Discussions:

Table 1:

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.813	24

Exploratory factor analysis method was used to sum up the complete set of items into desired factors and then proceed for linear regression.

Table2:

Reliability Analysis

Model	R	R-Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of The Estimate
1	.240	.057	.052	.97340215

Table3:

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	10.920	1	10.920	11.525	.001 ^a
	Residual	179.080	189	.948		
	Total	190.000	190			

a. Predictors: (Constant), GDP

b. Dependent Variable: EP

As looking at figure of Adjusted R Square that is 0.052 or 5.2% this is the overall fitness of the model which further clarifies gender discrimination factors are not contributing towards the employee performance in public sector universities employees of upper sindh but significance level is .001.

Table4:

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.752E-5	.070		.000	1.000
	GDP	.239	.070	.240	3.395	.001

a. Dependent Variable: EP

According to the Coefficient table only single variable that is gender discrimination in promotion is positively related with employee performance and level of significance is .001, but the strength of relationship between gender discrimination in promotion and employee performance/productivity is too much weak that is (.240), as concluded by (Francine & Jed, 2007).

Further suggestions:

Area of employee performance is too much debatable in different organizational set up but according to our results gender discrimination factors are not much contributing towards employee performance, Gap term is too much large to be worked out. There may be other factors or variables which contribute to employee performance.

Limitation:

1. Only the universities of Upper Sindh was the area of research,
2. Only the public sector universities was selected for conducting the survey

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